

VERITY Recommendations for Fostering Trust in Science

COLLABORATION

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Collaboration is crucial for fostering trust in science because trust is not built in isolation but emerges through the coordinated actions of diverse actors across the trust in science ecosystem. Researchers, educators, communicators, policymakers, funders, and civil society each play distinct but interconnected roles in shaping how science is produced, shared, understood, and used. VERITY's recommendations provide a roadmap for building a more participatory and sustainable trust in the science ecosystem by addressing collaboration gaps within research management, communication, inclusivity, and ethical practices. The emphasis is placed on **empowering partnerships, bridging institutional silos, and leveraging innovative strategies to create a dynamic interface between science and society.**

How to support collaboration to foster trust in science?

COLLABORATION:

Institutionalise and Strengthen Cross-Sector Collaboration

- Foster interdisciplinary, international, and cross-sector collaboration by creating multi-level platforms for knowledge exchange, best practice sharing, and policy development that actively involve policymakers, industry, educators, and civil society.
- Strengthen coordination both within and between policy makers, funders, scientific actors, and other relevant organisations, across departments, levels, and sectors, to overcome institutional silos and enable coherent policy implementation.
- Engage citizens in co-designing and evaluating research by addressing participation barriers, especially for marginalised groups such as those with lower educational attainment, economically vulnerable individuals, and older adults, and fostering inclusion through collaboration with local networks and community initiatives.

Enhance Collaboration through Mutual Understanding and Translation

- Build science-for-policy mechanisms that connect research with policy needs, ensuring timely and actionable outputs while safeguarding scientific freedom.

- Establish liaison offices and structured frameworks to translate scientific findings into policy-relevant insights and accessible messages for society.
- Encourage partnerships between industry, academia, and civil society to co-create science and align research with societal needs, ensuring transparency, accountability, and shared benefits.
- Create platforms for collaboration between Stewards of Trust, using innovative tools like games or story-writing, to share relatable narratives and foster mutual learning.

Foster Ethical and Open Research Practices

- Strengthen the culture of research ethics and integrity through inclusive collaboration between academic and non-academic stakeholders.
- Promote data sharing and interoperability to foster innovation and reduce redundancies.

Leverage Influential Stakeholders

- Engage trusted public figures, including community and religious leaders, to strengthen credibility, broaden outreach and deepen public engagement with science.
- Strengthen ties between all Stewards of Trust and local communities and build effective connections across diverse stakeholder groups.

Adopt Sustainable Collaboration

- Foster collaboration among Stewards of Trust by creating incentives and mutual benefits that encourage long-term partnerships.

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VERITY Recommendations on Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/records/16975899>

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